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INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE & INFORMATION SCIENCE
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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **AKASH SHETTY** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017-18**.

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms ARJUN P of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2017-18 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **HARSHITH** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017-18**.

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **JITHIN RAJ K** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017-18**.

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **JYOTHI** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017-18**.

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms KAUSHIK MP of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2017-18 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **KRITHIKA J** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017-18**.

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms MAHAMMAD of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2017-18 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms NARSANA MTP of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2017-18 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms NIVEDHITHA M of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2017-18 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms PRAKRITHI H of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2017-18 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms PRASHANTH of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2017-18 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **PRIYANKA K** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017-18**.

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms SAFIYA HM of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2017-18 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms SAVITHA of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2017-18 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms SNEHA M S of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2017-18 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms SUDARSHAN S of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2017-18 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **TILAK** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year **2017-18**.

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms VEEKSHITHA M of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2017-18 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms VIDYASHANKA of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2017-18 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms VIJAY of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2017-18 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms AGNEL of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2018-19 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **AYSHATH** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018-19**.

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **BASHEEMA** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2018-19 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **DHANUSHREE** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2018-19 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms HARSHITH MS of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2018-19 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms HARSHITHA DJ of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2018-19 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **IHTHISHAM** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2018-19 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **K SHRI** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2018-19 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **KARTHIK C** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year **2018-19**.

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms MALEEHA of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2018-19 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms MANOJ AMIN D of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2018-19 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms NAGAPRASAD of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2018-19 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms SHEIKH of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2018-19 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms YUSUF SHAIKH of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2018-19 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms ANJUSHA of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms ASHWATHI P K of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **ATHIRA A K** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms ATHULYAN of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms CHAITRA G RAI of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **DARSHAN KH** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms DEEKSHA IM of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms JANANI of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms KAUSALYA of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms LATHA of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms MAHESH of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms NAYANA N of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **OMPRASAD K** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms PAVITHRA of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms POOJA of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms POOJA A S of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **RAKSHITHA** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **RANJITH** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms RASHIDA K of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **RESHMA** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms SANATH of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms SANJANA SPAI of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms SHARAVYA of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms SHASHANKS of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms SHIFALI P of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **SINDHUSREE B** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms SOURAV K of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms SUJAY TY of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms SUSHMA A of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms SUZAIFA of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms VIGNESH of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **VINAYAJYOTHI** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms YASHASWINI of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2019-20 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms AHMED of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **AJITH N** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **ARATHI** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms ARAVINDA of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **AYSHATHUL** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **DARSHAN** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms DEEPIKA of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms FAZEENA of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms POOJA of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms MASHOOQUE of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms SANDHYA of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms SARISHMA V of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms SHWETHA of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms SHYAMJITH V S of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms SINDHUJA of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms SOWMYASHRE of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms ABDUL of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms ADITH of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms AMITH of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms ANISH of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms ASHITH RAIT of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms AVINASH K of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **DHEERAJ B** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms HARSHITH MS of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **JITHIYA JOHN** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **KARTHIK K** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms KAUSHIK M G of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms MADAN RAO M of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms MANOJ KUMAR of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms MATHEW M G of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms MOORTHY of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms NEELAM of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms NIKSHITHA S R of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms PRABIR MAITY of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms PRASADA K of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms RAHUL K of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **RAKSHITH P** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **RESHMA M** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms SACHIN M of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **SHRAVAN** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms SNEHA S G of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **SWATHI B B** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms VAISHAK NAIR of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **VICHITH** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms VIDYA SN of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2020-21 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **Abhirami T P** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Adhi Avinash of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Aishwarya A M of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Amrutha R of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Anagha K of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Anvitha R of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Archana K T of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Ashin K of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Ashwin of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **Bhoomika B R** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Deekshith of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Devichandana K of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Dinesh S of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Harshith S of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **Hithaishi** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **Kruthi P** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Lakshmi of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Mahendrakumar of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Murari Anand of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Pallavi S Shastri of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Pooja H B of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Pooja P G of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Prajwal of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Pramod Vishnu of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Prathiksha of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **Ruthuraj K V** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Sahana H J of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Sameeksha R of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Sangeetha S of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Saphthami D M of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Sapthami of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **Sharath Adiga** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Sharmila of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **Shilpa Krishna** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Shreya D Shetty of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **Sinchana A N** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Sudarshan B S of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Sumanth M of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Surendra of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Uchil Ninad of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **Varsha Puranik** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Yashaswini K of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Pranat of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Mahalaxmi Laddi of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Sahana D.M. of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Nagendra E of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **Abhishek** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Akash K S of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Avisha V of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Devipriya M of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Dhanraj of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Lavanya M P of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Mohammed of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Naheem of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **Raksha K R** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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Certificate of Participation

A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Rhea R Uppala of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Jowana Dhirshal of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms S Neema of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms SaiKiran C S of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms Sankalp M Shet of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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A hands-on certificate in **Data analysis using Python** course is awarded to Mr/Ms **Shibin Peter** of MCA for the successful completion of the course during the year 2021-22 .

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